

LuMISS – Miniaturized Spectrometer for Lunar In-situ Mineralogical Exploration

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Introduction: LuMISS (Lunar Mineralogical Imaging for Surface Studies) is a project developed in partnership between INAF – Istituto di Astrofisica e Planetologia Spaziali (INAF-IAPS), the University of Pavia (UniPV) and ASI (Agenzia Spaziale Italiana). LuMISS was selected by ESA following the Announcement of Opportunities “Reserve Pool of Science Activities for the Moon” issued in 2022. The project aims at defining a prototype of a Visible–Near Infrared (VNIR) spectrometer for the mineralogical characterization of the lunar regolith, with the capability to detect hydrated minerals, water ice and anhydrous mineralogical phases, as well as potential organic compounds. The LuMISS instrument is conceptually an evolution of the VNIR spectrometer Ma_MISS (Mars Multispectral Imager for Sub-surface Studies) designed to be flown onboard the ExoMars/Rosalind Franklin rover [1].

The scientific project addresses multiple objectives, ranging from understanding the formation and the evolution of the Moon to supporting the selection of scientifically valuable sampling sites and areas of interest for In-Situ Resource Utilization (ISRU).

Scientific objectives and background: The knowledge of the lunar surface is based on a vast amount of data collected over more than 50 years through telescopic observations, orbital missions, and lander/rover investigations. However, several scientific questions remain open and are still under investigation. These include:

- the composition of lunar rocks, in terms of compositional and textural variability within the highlands and maria, as well as variations with depth;
- the physico-chemical properties of the regolith and the processes governing its formation and interaction with space weathering;
- the lunar volcanism, with particular emphasis on the Moon’s evolution, the types and processes of magmatism, and how this information can be derived from rock analysis.
- the mineralogical characterization of lunar resources available for human exploration and the extent to which they can be derived from surface rocks;
- the acquisition and study of new lunar samples that differ from those already collected and are representative of previously unexplored regions of the lunar surface.

By using VNIR spectroscopy (0.3–2.5 μm range), it is possible to identify and characterize the main mineralogical phases composing the lunar surface, particularly anhydrous mafic silicates (pyroxenes, plagioclase, olivine) through the analysis of Fe^{2+} absorption bands near 1 and 2 μm [2,3]. A detailed study of the position of these absorption bands provides information on the type and composition of the pyroxenes present. Other materials, such as Fe-Ti oxides, opaque phases, and glasses, can also be identified within this spectral range.

Moreover, the VIS–NIR interval is sensitive to physical parameters such as grain size and records the effects of processes such as space weathering[4] (changes in spectral slope, reduction of albedo and spectral contrast, and reddening).

The study of the composition of surface rocks and lunar regolith at very small spatial scales—on the order of fractions of a millimeter—allows detailed characterization of materials, providing valuable information on textural relationships among mineralogical components, as well as on individual grains and inclusions.

LuMISS Instrument: The instrument has a modular architecture and consists of the following main subsystems: (i) an optical head mounted on a robotic arm or rover deck; (ii) a single optical fiber or fiber bundle; (iii) a spectrometer unit, including optical elements and a detector on the rover/lander.

The optical head design and lunar application represent new developments, particularly due to the significantly different thermal constraints of the lunar environment compared to the Martian case. Moreover, the scientific application to the knowledge of the regolith at small scale requires a new concept of OH and deployment.

Breadboarding of the instrument: The activities to be carried out for the prototype are summarized as follows:

- Trade-off analysis between scientific objectives, spectrometer type, and instrument performance;
- Study of deployment scenarios (e.g., robotic arm vs. rover deck mounting, alternative configurations);
- Optical head design, including evaluation of a possible focusing mechanism;
- Definition of operational modes for high-resolution hyperspectral image acquisition;
- Study of the illumination system;

- Assessment of system resources (mass, power consumption, data volume, etc.);
- Evaluation of the thermal environment and its impact on the instrument concept;
- Investigation of engineering solutions for thermal control of the instrument.

At the end of the study, a new optical head concept for a Ma_MISS-type spectrometer dedicated to close-up observations of the lunar surface or samples will be defined.

Acknowledgments

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References: [1] De Sanctis et al. (2017) (2017): *Astrobiology* 17, 6, 7. [2] Pieters, C., Klima, R., & Green, R., 2019. In J. Bishop, J. Bell III, & J. Moersch (Eds.), *Remote Compositional Analysis: Techniques for Understanding Spectroscopy, Mineralogy, and Geochemistry of Planetary Surfaces*, pp. 368-392. doi:10.1017/9781316888872.020. [3] Isaacson et al., 2011. *Meteoritics and Planetary Science* 46, 228–251. doi:10.1111/j.1945-5100.2010.01148.x . [4] Pieters, C. M., and S. K. Noble, 2016. *J. Geophys. Res. Planets*, 121, 1865–1884, doi:10.1002/2016JE005128